

Silver nanoparticle catalyzed degradation of textile dyes

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Abstract : Water pollution by the presence of organic and inorganic contaminants poses the major threat to human health. Presence of residue of textile dyes in water is the big concern for inhabitants. Several approaches using physical and chemical methods have been tried out for removal of these dyes from waste water. More recently green synthesized nanoparticles have become attractive catalyst for removal of dyes from textile effluents. The present work reports preparation of silver nanoparticles using aqueous leaf extract of *Ocimum tenuiflorum*. The prepared silver nanoparticles were tried out as green catalyst for the degradation of Methyl Orange and Rose Bengal using NaBH_4 as reducing agent. The results of dye degradation was monitored using UV-Visible spectrophotometer suggest that the nanoparticle worked as efficient catalyst during the degradation.

Keywords : Silver nanoparticles, textile dyes, *Ocimum tenuiflorum*.

Introduction

Development of green method for synthesis of nanoparticles (NPs) is the most focused branch of nanotechnology since it does not generate any hazardous waste¹⁻⁶.

Among the noble metals, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are the most widely used metal nanoparticles because of their potential applications in different applications.

Different methods⁷ have been employed to prepare AgNPs with variation in morphologies. Methods adopted include single-source precursor heat treatment at 550 °C, microwave-assisted synthesis, microwave-solvothermal synthesis, and solvothermal synthesis⁸. Other methods such as photochemical, ultraviolet, sonochemical and ultrasonic synthesis have also been exploited recently.

However, the existing methods have long procedures and processing times. It is therefore, considered necessary, to develop facile, energy-efficient and safe methods for the synthesis of metal nanoparticles.

Globally, textile industry effluent is a major contributor to water pollution since these dyes are highly coloured and resistant to degradation. Approximately 15% of these dyes end up as colouring materials in discharged effluents. Dyes containing azo group (-N=N-), occupy about half of the total world dye market. Azo dyes are also a major organic compounds released by many industries such as paper, plastic, leather, food, cosmetic and phar-

maceutical⁹.

Among these azo dyes, Methyl Orange (MO) serves as a model, water soluble compound, which is widely used in chemical, textile and paper industries and is harmful to the environment. Different physical and chemical methods such as adsorption, oxidation, coagulation, membrane filtration and photochemical degradation have been tried out for the removal of textile dyes from the effluents. Out of these methods adsorption is established as the most suitable and promising method because of its cost effectiveness, operational simplicity, low cost and low energy requirement.

The metal nanoparticles are known to exhibit good catalytic activity and selectivity towards degradation of textile dyes¹⁰. Hence, the present study attempts to use AgNPs synthesized using *Ocimum tenuiflorum* extract as a reducing and stabilizing agent. The synthesized nanoparticles have been tried as green catalyst for the degradation of MO, Rose Bengal (RB).

It is known that, degradation of MO and RB by sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) in absence of catalyst is thermodynamically favorable, but kinetically difficult. Hence the present work attempts to use AgNPs as green catalyst to overcome the kinetic barrier to facilitate degradation of MO and RB.

Materials and methods :

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4),

Methyl Orange and Rose Bengal were purchased from SD fine chemicals from India. *Ocimum tenuiflorum* was collected from the local fields on outcasts of Vellore.

Preparation of leaf extract :

10 g of fresh *Ocimum tenuiflorum* leaves were thoroughly washed, finely crushed, mixed with 20 mL of distilled water and boiled at 80 °C for 15 min. The resultant extract was filtered through Whatman filter paper and stored for further use.

FT-IR spectrum of the prepared leaf extract was taken on a JASCO FT-IR 4100 instrument using KBr pellet method, to identify the functional group which could be responsible for the reduction and stabilization of AgNPs (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectrum of plant extract.

The leaf extract showed absorption bands at 3045, 1641, 1394, 1083 and 682 cm^{-1} . For untreated sample the strongest absorption bands can be assigned carbonyl peak (C=O stretching) at 1623 cm^{-1} , indicating carboxylate content in the plant, which may be responsible for the reduction of metal ion to metal nanoparticles.

Green synthesis of AgNPs :

To a 50 mL of 1 mM aqueous AgNO_3 solution, 0.5 mL of prepared leaf extract was added. Formation of AgNPs was monitored by measuring absorbance of the

solution using UV-Visible spectrophotometer (JASCO V 670). The peak at the 436 nm indicated formation of AgNPs (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectrum of AgNPs.

Characterization of AgNPs :

The prepared nanoparticles were characterized using FT-IR spectroscopy (Fig. 3) and high resolution trans-

Fig. 3. FT-IR spectrum of prepared AgNPs.

mission electron microscope (HR-TEM) (Fig. 4), for understanding the particle size and morphology.

Fig. 4. TEM image of AgNPs.

The FT-IR spectrum shows typical absorption bands which indicate formation of AgNPs.

The HR-TEM image indicates that the formed AgNPs were spherical with average particle size of 30 nm.

Catalytic degradation of MO and RB :

The prepared AgNPs were used as green catalyst for NaBH₄ assisted degradation of MO and RB dyes. The process of degradation was monitored by measuring the reduction in the absorbance of the dye on a UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Results and discussion

2.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ NaBH₄ and 2.5×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ of prepared AgNPs solution were added to a solution of MO (5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) and change in the absorbance was monitored at 464 nm (Fig. 5).

Similarly, the degradation of RB (1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) was carried out by adding NaBH₄ (5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) and AgNPs solution (5×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³) to the dye solution. The change the absorbance was measured 547 nm on a UV-Visible spectrophotometer and data is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5. Degradation of MO using NaBH₄ in the presence of prepared AgNPs.

Fig. 6. UV-Visible spectra of degradation RB during the catalyzed reduction.

Conclusion

A simple green method of synthesizing AgNPs using leaf extract of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* as reducing and stabilizing agent has been described. The prepared AgNPs were used as green catalyst for assisting the degradation of MO and RB dyes with NaBH₄ as the reducing agent.

From the data of the degradation process, it could be concluded that the green synthesized AgNPs performed satisfactorily as catalyst during the degradation process of the dyes used.

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